

The Influence of Organizational Climate and Effective Communication on Employee Engagement through Employee Morale at the Educational Dental and Oral Hospital Nala Husada Surabaya

Dwiane Risalona¹

¹Student: Master of Management

Sukesi²

²Lecturer of Master of Management Business

Dr. Soetomo

Faculty of Economics and Business University Surabaya

Abstract:- Changes in the work environment caused by the outbreak and end of the COVID-19 pandemic have forced humans to adapt to limitations and return to new normal conditions. Changes in the way and work environment ultimately have an impact on employee work attitudes towards the organization. This study aims to analyze the effect of organizational climate and effective communication on employee engagement through employee morale at the Nala Husada Dental and Oral Education Hospital in Surabaya. This type of research is explanatory research with a quantitative method approach. The data collection method used a questionnaire distributed to 60 employees of the Nala Husada Dental and Oral Education Hospital in Surabaya. The data analysis technique used is Structural Equation Modeling analysis using Partial Least Square. The results of the study show that effective communication has a direct and significant effect on employee morale and employee engagement. Employee morale also has a significant direct influence on employee engagement. Organizational climate and effective communication have a significant indirect effect on employee engagement. This study suggests increasing employee engagement through increasing effective communication combined with programs that can improve the organizational climate and employee morale at the Nala Husada Dental and Oral Education Hospital in Surabaya. Organizational climate and effective communication have a significant indirect effect on employee engagement. This study suggests increasing employee engagement through increasing effective communication combined with programs that can improve the organizational climate and employee morale at the Nala Husada Dental and Oral Education Hospital in Surabaya. Organizational climate and effective communication have a significant indirect effect on employee engagement. This study suggests increasing employee engagement through increasing effective communication combined with programs that can improve the organizational climate and employee morale at the Nala Husada Dental and Oral Education Hospital in Surabaya.

Keywords:- Organizational Climate, Effective Communication, Employee Morale, Employee Engagement.

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 changed all aspects of human life. The need for individuals to increase their vigilance and keep their distance forces all levels of society to change their living habits, including at work. As an effort to protect its workforce, every organization is forced to change the way it works, starting from working from home or taking shifts to the layout in each workspace. All of these requirements have an impact on how to interact between co-workers and how to work.

As a health service provider facility that has an Emergency Unit, Dental and Oral Education Hospital Nala Husada Surabaya must continue to operate by implementing COVID-19 safety and security standards and requiring all employees to adapt.

The relaxation of health protocols related to the Covid-19 pandemic began to change in mid-2022 and the World Health Organization (WHO) stated that the Covid-19 pandemic had ended on May 5 2023 again bringing changes and demanding new adjustments. This change ultimately had an impact on Nala Husada hospital employees service providers, both health workers and non-health workers.

In the field of health care, a positive organizational climate is an important concept because it relates to employee attitudes and leads to organizational commitment. Attitudes and perceptions of employees will affect the hospital services provided by health workers. The work attitude of employees in the organization is influenced by the work environment and the changes that occur in it. Employee work behavior which is a personal characteristic and work environment, climate is an important aspect to study (Berberoglu, 2018).

A better psychological climate for employees can be created from a human-oriented culture so that it can provide a feeling of belonging, dedication to caring for employees in the organization. Without a positive organizational climate, organizational performance will also be difficult to develop (Hussainy, 2022).

Kalhor, et al (2018) stated that dynamic communication between organizational members will lead to employees' willingness to accept more responsibility in achieving organizational goals. This is obtained from a more efficient organizational climate.

Individuals in the organization come from different environments, educational to economic backgrounds, bringing physiological, psychological, and biographical factors into the organization. Activities within the organization including changes in the way of interacting at work are parts that must be planned, coordinated and evaluated in an effort to achieve organizational goals by going through the communication process (Yusnita, 2021)

Research by Dominguez et al in Luna-Pereira, et al (2022) found that the dimensions that most influence the relationship between organizational climate and productivity include structure, communication, leadership. Shrivastava and Prasad (2019) argued for the importance of effective communication in all functions in the workplace. Various studies have proven that communication is a skill that needs to be trained effectively in the workplace because it can increase organizational productivity and performance.

With the current workplace conditions that have employees from different generations and age groups, differences in attitudes, beliefs and ways of thinking must be balanced by the right communication patterns to avoid conflict. Communication plays a role in launching activities within the organization. Effective communication is important in organizational development because it is a tool that helps managers to carry out basic management functions such as planning, managing, providing motivation to exercising control.

Research by Indrasari, et al (2019) showed how organizational communication affects employee performance in addition to compensation and career paths. Employees will be motivated to achieve high performance because they feel compelled to carry out their work properly. The combination of mutual assistance and interdependence among employees that influences employee interaction at work is created by good communication within the organization.

Effective communication is an important basic tool for achieving organizational goals because communication is used by managers in making decisions that affect organizational performance. Functioning as a liaison between decision makers and all employees, effective communication is an important strategy for organizations to survive because communication can make and break organizational existence (Musheke and Phiri, 2021)

An organization needs to create a positive impact on the minds of employees to form positive work morale as well. This positive impact will make employees have trust and a strong relationship with the organization. In the end, employee trust in the organization will create positive morale at work (Fard, 2010).

The level of perception, attitude and feelings of employees towards the organization refers to mental status which is then understood as moral. Employee morale is often a positive and negative unity based on the geographical environment (Handini, et al, 2020). Research by Indrasari, et al (2019) states that employee morale will increase and motivate employees to carry out work in accordance with responsibilities and job descriptions if career planning is accepted by employees in accordance with the career opportunities provided by the organization.

Employee innovation and innovative behavior can be predicted through employee morale when linked to organizational performance or employee engagement. High employee morale can be seen from work involvement and commitment to positive organizational goals because there is manager support, clear work roles, low levels of stress and absenteeism and strong performance (Danaeefard & Torshab, 2021).

In a hospital environment where there is a great need for high work efficiency and attention to specific professions, employees need to be dedicated to work, the organization and the goals attached to the organization. Various studies have shown that work productivity, citizenship behavior, job satisfaction and high-performance result from high employee engagement (Bakker, 2017).

According to Handini, et al (2020), in general employees who feel valued will produce individuals with high work productivity, connect employees from top to bottom and make employees engaged and loyal to the organization. In the end, engaged employees can help increase organizational productivity.

Nala Husada Hospital Surabaya is a speciality hospital where young dentists undergo professional education at the Faculty of Dentistry, Hang Tuah University, Surabaya to become dentists. With a total of 60 employees with age, experience, years of service, gender, educational and socio-economic backgrounds, Nala Husada hospital is a diverse organization and influences the dynamics and interactions between employees.

From the views and dynamics described above, this study has the following hypothesis:

- H1: Organizational climate has a significant effect on employee morale at RSGMP Nala Husada Surabaya;
- H2: Organizational climate has a significant effect on employee engagement at RSGMP Nala Husada Surabaya;
- H3: Effective communication has a significant effect on employee morale at RSGMP Nala Husada Surabaya;
- H4: Effective communication has a significant effect on employee engagement in RSGMP Nala Husada Surabaya;
- H5: Employee morale has a significant effect on employee engagement at RSGMP Nala Husada Surabaya;
- H6: Organizational climate and effective communication affect employee engagement through employee morale at RSGMP Nala Husada Surabaya.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Organizational Climate

The term organizational climate has been understood in various ways such as feeling, atmosphere, environment, enthusiasm, visible conditions, organizational color and/or organizational personality. Like an organization, every employee has their own rules, goals and objectives. All of these interrelated things create an organizational climate (Kelvin-Iloafu, 2016). Employee behavior in organizations is the result of personal characteristics and the work environment. In this case, organizational climate is an important aspect for understanding employee behavior related to work.

Mullins (2010) argues, if organizational culture is defined as 'how work gets done in this workplace, then organizational climate is defined as 'how it feels to work in this place'. Organizational climate is a psychological climate in the aggregate which relates to individual perceptions of the work environment. Organizational climate has a very strong influence on employee attitudes on the sense of belonging, personal relationships and work performance.

Research by Kalhor, et al (2018) found that managers in health service organizations can achieve their goals by understanding the organizational climate of the hospital and its effect on employee work engagement which in turn can lead to a positive work attitude, enthusiasm in the organization and organizational commitment.

Hussainy (2022) explains that there is an orientation in explaining organizational climate as follows:

➤ *People-oriented organizational climate*

Organizational climate that looks at the dynamics that occur among employees such as fair treatment, mutual respect, how employees are rewarded for their contributions and the formation of a work life balance culture so as to create a positive work environment;

➤ *Rule-oriented organizational climate*

Organizational climate that emphasizes the rules and regulations applied to ensure that all employees refer to the same norms;

➤ *Goal-oriented organizational climate*

Organizational climate that emphasizes behaviors within the organization that are in line with the environment created by the organization to motivate employees to achieve the desired organizational goals;

➤ *Innovation-oriented organizational climate*

Organizational climate sees the efforts made by the company in creating a creative mindset to develop new ideas and innovations.

B. Effective Communication

As complex organizations, companies must develop communication channels to move up, down, and across the organizational structure. Downward communication allows managers to apply decisions and influence to employees under them and is used to disseminate information that is

under top management control. Meanwhile, upward communication allows those at lower levels to communicate their ideas and feelings to decision makers at higher levels (Gomez-Mejia, et al, 2007).

In organizations, although employees spend most of their time communicating, not all meaningful communication has taken place in the exchange of messages. Communication does not occur until information and understanding have been clearly provided between the sender and the intended recipient (Adu-Oppong, et al, 2014 in Shrivastava & Prasad, 2019).

Effective managerial communication is part of an organization's strategy in achieving its vision and mission and is important in creating collaboration in the work environment that has an impact on organizational performance and decision making. Effective communication can improve organizational relations and minimize disputes and strikes. Sometimes the vision and mission of the organization cannot be achieved due to ineffective communication. Lack of effective communication is one of the main reasons for confusion and bad planning in organizations.

Effective communication occurs when the desired effect is the result of the intentional or unintentional sharing of information. This effect ensures messages are not distorted during communication. Effective communication must produce the desired effect and maintain that effect with the potential for increased effect so that effective communication is in accordance with the desired goals (Antony, 2013).

Research conducted by Kube in 2014 (in Musheke et al, 2021) concluded that communication must be carried out in an open communication environment so that organizational performance can be effective.

Antony (2013) explains the important things that must exist in effective communication, both written and oral, namely:

- **Complete:** the communication must convey all the facts required by the recipient. The sender of the message must consider the recipient's thinking and adjust the delivery of the message;
- **Brief:** delivery of messages with the minimum possible words without setting aside other important things from communication;
- **Have Consideration:** effective communication must consider the recipient's point of view, background, mindset, level of education and others;
- **Clarity:** emphasizing a specific message or goal at a particular moment, not trying to achieve multiple goals at once;
- **Concrete:** specific and clear, clear and general;
- **Politeness:** The message conveyed shows the expression of the sender of the message while respecting the recipient of the message;
- **Accuracy:** no grammatical errors in communication.

C. Employee Morale

Employee morale is a determining factor for organizational health and is important because organizational performance and efficiency depend on it. An organization needs to create a positive influence on the minds of its employees to get positive employee morale. Creating employee morale is important for human resource management because employee performance and efficiency depend on employee morale.

A positive work attitude is generally seen as an important indication of how well things are going and seen as the ultimate condition for achieving one's goals. Conversely, low morale contributes to workforce problems, labor grievances, and a negative organizational climate (Cherrington, 1995).

According to Bowles and Cooper (2009) moral is defined as a state of psychological well-being of a person based on self-confidence, usefulness and purpose. Ransom in Senthilnathan and Rukshani (2015) states that high employee morale in an organization has more influence on productivity than competition.

Mallik et al (2019) explain moral as a concept that refers to how positive and supportive a group of people are towards the organization in which they are a part and the special feelings that group members share with others such as trust, self-esteem, purpose, pride in achievement and belief in leadership. and organizational success. Others explain employee morale as self-confidence or optimism experienced by a person or group of people in general, especially if it affects discipline and self-will.

Giese and Ruter in Nur et al (2021) found that there is an important association between employee morale and productivity. Baehr and Renck's research in Nur et al (2021) further investigated the moral structure of employees and concluded five basic subjective factors, namely:

- Employee-management relations
- Direct supervision of managers
- Incentive
- Friendly attitude from fellow employees
- Job satisfaction in terms of self-actualization.

D. Employee Engagement

The concept of Employee Engagement was first put forward by Kahn (1990) through the theory of personal engagement. Kahn believes that employees play engagement in their work roles at work. Kahn examines psychological factors related to employee engagement and disengagement in the workplace and concludes that various factors at various levels, namely individual, interpersonal, group, in-group and organizational, will ultimately shape employee engagement and disengagement in the workplace.

Engagement theory was later developed by Maslach, Schaufeli and Leiter (2001) when they conceptualized job burnout and analyzed that engagement is separate from existing constructs in organizational psychology such as organizational commitment, job satisfaction and job involvement. Engagement construction focuses on work. Engagement provides a more complex and holistic perspective on the individual's relationship to work. Maslach et al said that employee engagement is a state of persistent positive affection for employees characterized by passion, dedication, and absorption. Passion refers to a high level of energy and toughness, a willingness to put effort into a task, the ability not to tire easily and to persist in the face of difficulties.

Saks (2006) defines engagement as the extent to which a person pays attention and absorbs performance in the unique and different cognitive, emotional and behavioral components associated with one's performance role. Shuck & Wollard (2010) defines the concept of employee engagement as a state of cognitive, emotional and employee behavior that is directed towards the desired organizational goals.

Bailey et al (2017) found that engagement is positively associated with individual morale, performance, additional work and organizational performance. From the same research it was also found that the moral results of engagement were divided into two main points: well-being and perceptions of health and attitudes related to employees' work in the workplace.

E. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework formulated in this study is shown in the following figure:

Fig. 3.2: conceptual framework

➤ **Information:**

- Direct Influence
- --- direct follow-up effect

F. Analysis Models

The Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis model in this study can be modeled on the following equation:

- Employee morale (Z) = β_1 Organizational Climate (X1) + β_2 Effective Communication (X2)
- Employee Engagement (Y) = β_1 Organizational climate (X1) + β_2 Effective Communication (X2) + β_3 Employee Morale (Z)

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Operational Definition, Variable Identification, and Variable Indicators.

Variables Which used in this study can be identified as follows:

➤ Independent Variable

- Organizational Climate (X1)
- Effective Communication (X2)

➤ Intervening Variables

The intervening variable in this study is Employee Morale.

➤ Dependent Variable

The dependent variable in this study is Employee Engagement.

The operational definitions of the variables in this study are as follows:

B. Organizational Climate (X1)

Mullins (2010) argues, if organizational culture is defined as 'how work gets done in this workplace, then organizational climate is defined as 'how it feels to work in this place'. Organizational climate is a psychological climate in the aggregate which relates to individual perceptions of the work environment. Organizational climate has a very strong influence on employee attitudes on the sense of belonging, personal relationships and work performance.

Organizational climate in this study is measured through several indicators according to Yusnita (2021), namely:

- Management support (X1.1);
- task clarity (X1.2);
- attractiveness of duties and responsibilities (X1.3);
- Freedom in conveying ideas (X1.4);
- Recognition of achievements (X1.5);
- Challenges at work (X1.6).

C. Effective Communication (X2)

Effective communication occurs when the desired effect is the result of the intentional or unintentional sharing of information. This effect ensures messages are not distorted during communication. Effective communication must produce the desired effect and maintain that effect with the potential for increased effect so that effective communication is in accordance with the desired goals (Antony, 2013). Antony explained the important things that must exist in effective communication, both written and oral, namely:

- Complete (X2.1)
- Compact (X2.2)
- Have Consideration (X2.3)
- Clarity (X2.4)
- Concrete (X2.5)
- Politeness (X2.6)
- Precision (X2.7)

D. Intervening Variable (Z)

Employee morale is a state of psychological well-being of a person based on self-confidence, usefulness and purpose. Employee morale in this study is measured through several indicators based on the research of Malik, et al (2019), namely:

- Belonging (Z.1)
- Open communication (Z.2)
- Recognition and awards (Z.3)
- Career opportunities (Z.3)
- Training and development (Z.4)

E. Dependent Variable (Y)

Shuck & Wollard (2010) define employee engagement as a positive psychological state that is active and tied to work that is operationalized by the intensity and direction of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral energy. Measurement of Employee Engagement in this study will use The Employee Engagement Scale (EES) developed by Shuck, et al (2016) with indicators:

- Cognitive (Y.1)
- Emotional (Y.2)
- Behavior (Y.3)

F. Sample population

The population in this study were 60 employees of Dental and Oral Hospital Nala Husada Surabaya. This study used a total sampling of 60 employees Nala Husada Educational Oral and Dental Hospital of Surabaya.

G. Data Types and Sources

The type of data used in this research is quantitative using questionnaires distributed to employees at Nala Husada Educational Oral and Dental Hospital Surabaya. The type of research used is explanatory research. Primary data in this study were obtained through questionnaires which were distributed to respondents which were arranged based on predetermined variables by providing alternative answers.

H. Data collection technique

The data collection technique used in this study was the method of distributing questionnaires with Likert scale.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Validity and Reliability Test

In this study, researchers conducted a pre-test by distributing questionnaires to 60 respondents. Then, the pre-test results were processed using IBM Statistics SPSS, to test the validity of each variable indicator. Measurement of the validity of each indicator is assessed based on KMO, Bartlett Test of Sphericity, Factor Loadings, and Anti Image. The results of pre-test data processing are shown in the following table.

Table 1: Validity Test

No	Variables	Code	KMO ≥ 0.5	Sig <0.05	MSA >0.50	Loading factor ≥ 0.5	Validity
1	ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE	OC 1	0.806	0.000	0.762	0.559	VALID
		OC 2			0.803	0.576	VALID
		OC 3			0.795	0.550	VALID
		OC 4			0.864	0.945	VALID
		OC 5			0.837	0.706	VALID
		OC 6			0.765	0.502	VALID
2	EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION	EC 1	0.734	0.000	0.867	0.979	VALID
		EC 2			0.679	0.644	VALID
		EC 3			0.902	0.965	VALID
		EC 4			0.657	0.973	VALID
3	EMPLOYEE MORALE	EM 1	0.668	0.000	0.846	0.626	VALID
		EM 2			0.582	0.972	VALID
		EM 3			0.616	0.973	VALID
		EM 4			0.621	0.955	VALID
		EM 5			0.714	0.851	VALID
4	EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT	EE 1	0.617	0.000	0.616	0.973	VALID
		EE 2			0.596	0.967	VALID
		EE 3			0.755	0.896	VALID

Based on the results of the validity test listed in the table above, it can be seen that the four variables namely Organizational Climate, Effective Communication,

Employee Morale and Employee Engagement have been declared valid because they are above 0.5.

Table 2: Convergent Validity Test Results

Variable	Statement Items	Factor Loadings	(AVE)	Composite Reliability
Organizational Climate	IO 1	0.559	0.872	0.953
	IO 2	0.576		
	IO 3	0.550		
	IO 4	0.945		
	IO 5	0.706		
	IO 6	0.502		
Effective Communication	EC 1	0.979	0.858	0.800
	EC 2	0.644		
	EC 3	0.965		
	EC 4	0.973		
Employee Morale	EM 1	0.626	0.915	0.943
	EM 2	0.972		
	EM 3	0.973		
	EM 4	0.955		
	EM 5	0.851		
Employee Engagement	EE 1	0.973	0.926	0.947
	EE 2	0.967		
	EE 3	0.896		

Table 2 reports the results of the CFA which show that all statement items for each variable used in this study have a factor loading value greater than 0.7, all AVE values are greater than 0.5, and composite reliability values (CR) all are greater than 0.5. Thus, these values confirm convergent validity in this study and explain that all statement items from each of the variables used in this study can be declared valid.

The Pearson correlation between the variables in this study is reported in table 3 showing that the highest correlation between variables is between locus of control and compensation with a correlation value of 0.866, which means that locus of control and compensation have a relationship or are interrelated with each other. The results also show that all the variables in this study have a correlation with each other.

Table 3: Correlation Test and Discriminant Validity

Variable	OC	EC	EM	EE
OC	0.966			
EC	0.655***	0.973		
EM	0.562***	0.8***	0.931	
EE	0.815***	0.7***	0.8***	0.934

Note: ***Significant at the 0.001 level;

Furthermore, from table 3, the numbers in a diagonal position in bold are the square root values of AVE whose value is greater than any correlation value below it. This

explains that the discriminant validity in this study can be confirmed and explains that all statement items from each of the variables used in this study can be declared valid.

Table 4: Reliability Test Results

Variable	Statement Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Organizational Climate	OC 1	0.858
	OC 2	
	OC 3	
	OC 4	
	OC 5	
	OC 6	
Effective Communication	EC 1	0.915
	EC 2	
	EC 3	
	EC 4	
Employee Morale	EM 1	0.926
	EM 2	
	EM 3	
	EM 4	
	EM 5	
Employee Engagement	EE 1	0.926
	EE 2	
	EE 3	

Table 4 shows the results of the reliability test in this study, the results show that the Cronbach's Alpha value for each of the variables discussed in this study is greater than 0.7, this explains that all the variables discussed in this study are reliable.

B. Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing in this study used the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis technique. SEM analysis in this study was carried out using a statistical application, namely SmartPLS 4 SEM model in the research presented in the following figure:

Fig. 2: SEM models

Table 5: Structural Test Results

hypothesis	Track			Estimates	t Value	P Value	Conclusion
H1	OC	◇	EM	0.053	0.396	0.692	Rejected
H2	OC	◇	EE	0.022	0.373	0.709	Rejected
H3	EC	◇	EM	0.015	63,226	0.000	Accepted
H4	EC	◇	EE	0.069	3,850	0.000	Accepted
H5	EM	◇	EE	0.070	10.423	0.000	Accepted

The results presented in Table 5.13 show that hypothesis testing is carried out based on significant values, p-values, and t-values. If the significant value is 0.05, the p-value is <0.05, and the t-value is > 1.96, then the hypothesis is accepted.

- H1: Based on the results of data processing, the t-value of H1 is 0.396, which is smaller than the t-table value of 1.96. And the H1 p-value is 0.692, greater than 0.05. So, hypothesis 1 is rejected, with organizational climate decisions having a positive influence but a weak and insignificant relationship to employee morale.
- H2: Based on the results of data processing, the t-value of H1 is 0.373, which is smaller than the t-table value of 1.96. And the H1 p-value is 0.709, greater than 0.05. So, hypothesis 2 is rejected, with organizational climate decisions having a positive but weak but not significant effect on employee engagement.

- H3: Based on the results of data processing, the t-value of H1 is 63.226, greater than the t-table value of 1.96. And the H1 p-value is 0.000, less than 0.05. So, hypothesis 3 is accepted, with effective communication decisions having a significant influence on employee morale.
- H4: Based on the results of data processing, the t-value of H1 is 3.850, greater than the t-table value of 1.96. And the H1 p-value is 0.000, less than 0.05. So, hypothesis 4 is accepted, with effective communication decisions having a significant effect on employee engagement.
- H5: Based on the results of data processing, the t-value of H1 is 10.423, greater than the t-table value of 1.96. And the H1 p-value is 0.000, less than 0.05. So, hypothesis 5 is accepted, with employee moral decisions having a significant effect on employee engagement.

Table 6: Mediation Effect Test Results

Hypothesis	Path					Est	T Value	P Value	Conclusion
H6	OC	◇	EM	◇	EE	0.038	2,405	0.001	Accepted
	EC	◇	EM	◇	EE	0.071	9,881	0.000	Accepted

H6: Based on the results of the mediation effect test in table 5.14 above, the H6 OC (organizational climate) is 2.405 and EC (Effective Communication) is 9,881 which is greater than the t-table value of 1.96. And the H6 p-value is 0.001 and 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. So, hypothesis 6 is accepted, with Organizational Climate and Effective Communication decisions influencing Employee Engagement through Employee Morale.

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the descriptive analysis test for each of the variables discussed in this study, it was explained that each of the variables studied, such as organizational climate, effective communication, employee morale and employee engagement were included in the very good category. That is, organizational climate, effective communication, employee morale and employee engagement at Educational Oral and Dental Hospital of Nala Husada in Surabaya is very good.

Organizational climate variables at the Education Dental and Oral Hospital Nala Husada Surabaya based on the results of the analysis of the answers of the respondents who strongly agreed that the most attention was paid to the attractiveness of tasks and responsibilities while the answers that disagreed the most were challenges at work. This shows that organizational climate, has a positive correlation with employee engagement. This is supported by research conducted by Hadiyatno (2018) in Obeng, et al (2021) stating

that organizational climate is the perception of objective working conditions, consisting of organizational characteristics and the form of relationships between employees when carrying out work. In line with previous studies, Mohanta, et al (2023) defines organizational climate as the perception of shared meaning from employees regarding policies, practices, and procedures encountered, as well as observed behaviors that are rewarded, supported and expected by the organization.

Analysis results on effective communication variables at the Dental and Oral Education Hospital of Nala Husada Surabaya, the answers from the respondents who strongly agreed were mostly awareness and understanding, while the answers that disagreed the most were involvement in communication. As a complex organization, management must develop communication channels to move up, down, and across the organizational structure. Downward communication allows managers to apply decisions and influence to employees under them and is used to disseminate information that is under top management control. Meanwhile, upward communication allows those at lower levels to communicate their ideas and feelings to decision makers at higher levels (Gomez-Mejia, et al, 2007). Therefore, Educational Oral and Dental Hospital of Nala Husada Surabaya must improve involvement in employee communication so that effective communication can be achieved accordingly. In this case, management must be open and always involve employees in general decision making

and maintain and increase awareness and understanding of employee duties and responsibilities.

Meanwhile, on employee moral variable at the Education Dental and Oral Hospital Nala Husada Surabaya based on the results of the analysis of the answers of the respondents who strongly agreed that the most were training and development while the answers that disagreed the most were recognition and appreciation. Mallik et al (2019) explained moral as a concept that refers to how positive and supportive a group of people are towards the organization in which they are a part and the special feelings that group members share with others such as trust, self-esteem, purpose, pride in achievement and belief in leadership. and organizational success. Others explain employee morale as the confidence or optimism experienced by a person or group of people in general, especially if it affects discipline and self-will. Hospital management must improve and pay attention to the recognition and appreciation of employees. This is important because it relates to the psychological condition of employees, as well as maintain and provide employee training and development. The psychological condition of employees is one of the benchmarks for employee's comfort, confidence and productivity in carrying out their duties so that employee morale is always stable and well controlled.

On employee engagement variable, based on the results of the analysis of the answers of the respondents who strongly agreed, the most respondents were behavioral, while the answers that disagreed were mostly emotional. This is in accordance with what was conveyed by Shuck & Wollard (2010) who defined the concept of employee engagement as a cognitive, emotional and behavioral state of employees that is directed towards the desired organizational goals. Bailey et al (2017) found that engagement is positively associated with individual morale, performance, additional work and organizational performance. From the same research, it was also found that the moral results of engagement are two main points: well-being and perceptions of health and attitudes related to work. Therefore, hospital must increase and pay attention to the emotionality of employees, namely employees must also have respect for agencies so that organizational goals can be achieved to the fullest.

Furthermore, based on the results of hypothesis testing explained that effective communication and employee morale had a significant positive effect on employee engagement. Additionally, the findings in this study explain that organizational climate does not have a significant or positive but weak effect on employee morale and employee engagement. Finally, the results of this study explain that organizational climate and effective communication have a significant positive effect on employee engagement through employee morale. The results of this study support the findings of previous studies, Sahni (2021) found that job characteristics are positively and significantly related to employee engagement, job satisfaction is positively and significantly associated with employee engagement. Kelvin-Iloafu (2016) explains that there is a strong correlation between effective communication and the company's level of success. There is a positive correlation between effective communication and achievement of organizational goals.

Musheke and Phiri (2021) in their research stated that there was no significant relationship between management and the communication channels used. There was a relationship between the communication channels used and effective communication. Effective communication has a positive effect on organizational performance.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion above, while organizational climate has positive influence yet significant enough to employee morale and employee engagement. On the other hand, effective communication and employee morale have has a positive and significant impact on employee morale and employee engagement. As employee morale has positive and significant effect to employee engagement, it's safe to say that organizational climate and effective communication have positive effect to employee engagement trough employee morale as intervening variable.

Based on the research results and conclusions in this study, some suggestions arise as issues for consideration to resolve related organizational problems such as organizational climate, effective communication, employee morale and employee engagement such as opportunities for employees to learn new things in their jobs. It is also always a good practice for hospital management to open to employees so that they can channel ideas and opinions to achieve vision and mission accordingly. Soft and hard skill trainings for employees can also be expected to support employee's productivity that leads to organization performance. Employee's recognition and appreciation will bring organization even further in creating healthy and positive employee morale. With a healthy and positive employee morale, management has easier job in encouraging employee's behavior and creating great team that are expected to support its purpose and goals.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Antony, A. 2013. Impact of Effective Communication on Labor Productivity in Civil Engineering Projects: A Case of Kampala Central Division.
- [2.] Anugwom, GA 2007. Issues, Principals Techniques and Practice in Administration and Management. Enugu: El'Denmark Publishers.
- [3.] Astari, K., Kadiyono, AL, Batubara, M. 2022. "Adaptation of the Employee Engagement Scale (EES) Measuring Tool". Journal of Economics and Business, Vol. 11 no. July 1, 2022. (511-520)
- [4.] Bailey, C., Madden, A., Alfes, K., and Fletcher, L. 2017. "The Meaning, Antecedents and Outcomes of Employee Engagement: A Narrative Synthesis". International Journal of Management Reviews, Vol 19. (31-53).
- [5.] Bakker, AB 2017. "Strategic and Proactive Approaches to Work Engagement". Organizational Dynamics, 46. (67-75)
- [6.] Berberogly, A. 2018. "Impact of Organizational Climate on Organizational Commitment and Perceived Organizational Performance: Empirical

- Evidence from Public Hospitals. Berberoglu BMC Health Services Research (18:399).
- [7.] Churchill, GA, Ford, NM, Walker, OC 1976. "Organizational Climate and Job Satisfaction in the Sales Force". *Journal of Marketing Res*, 13. (323-332).
- [8.] Fard, HD, Ghahari, AR, & Hasiri, A. 2010. "Organizational Trust in the Public Sector: Explaining the Role of Managers' Managerial Competency". *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 25. (29-43).
- [9.] Handini, S., Sukesi., Baharuddin., Paranoan, N., Lydia, L. 2020. "Effect of the Environment of Workplace in the Growth of an Efficient Business System". *Journal of Critical Reviews*, Vol 7, Issue 1. (246-250)
- [10.] Hussainy, SS 2022. "Organizational Climate: From Literature Review to Agenda Ahead". *International Journal of Engineering Technologies and Management Research*, 9(1), 44-62.
- [11.] Indrasari, M., Syamsudin, N., Purnomo, BR, Yunus, E. 2019. "Compensation, Organizational Communication, and Career Path as Determinants of Employee Performance Improvement". *Humanities & Social Reviews* Vol. 7(4). (956-961)
- [12.] Kahn, WA 1990. "Psychological Conditions of Personal Engagement and Disengagement at Work". *Academy of Management Journal*, 33(4). (692-724).
- [13.] Kalhor, R., Khosravizadeh, O., Moosavi, S., Heidari, M., Habibi, H. 2018. Role of Organizational Climate in Job Involvement: A Way to Develop the Organizational Commitment of Nursing Staff. *Journal of Evidence-Based Integrative Medicine*, Vol. 23. (1-5).
- [14.] Kelvin-Iloafu, L. 2016. The Role of Effective Communication in Strategic Management of Organizations. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, Vol. 6, No. 12: December 2016. (93-101).
- [15.] Mallik, A., Mallik, L., and Keerthi. 2019. "Impact of Employee Morale on Organizational Success". *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, Vol. 8 Issue 4, November 2019.(3289-3293).
- [16.] Maslach, C., Schaufeli, WB, & Leiter, MP 2001. "Job Burnout". *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52(1). (397-422).
- [17.] Mullins, L. 2010. "Management and Organizational Behavior". 9th edition. Pearson Education.
- [18.] Musheke, MM, & Phiri, J. 2021. The Effects of Effective Communication on Organizational Performance Based on the Systems Theory. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 9. (659-671)
- [19.] Neely, GH 1999. "The Relationship Between Employee Morale and Employee Productivity". *Fire Services Financial Management*, Oklahoma. 1-12
- [20.] Nnamseh, M. 2009. "The Role of Communication in Business Success". *Nigerian Journal of Management Research*, 1. (4).
- [21.] Nur, F., Harrison, D., Deb, S., Burch, RF and Strawderman, L. 2021. "Identification of Interventions to Improve Employee Morale in Physically Demanding, Repetitive Motion Work Tasks: A Pilot Case Study. *Congent Engineering Journal*, 8. (1-17).
- [22.] Shuck, B., Adelson, JL, Reio Jr, TG 2016. *Human Resource Management*, November-December 2017, Vol. 56, No. 6. (953-977).
- [23.] Sahni, J. 2021. "Employee Engagement Among Millennial Workforce: Empirical Study on Selected Antecedents and Consequences". *SAGE Open*, January-March 2021. (1-13)
- [24.] Saks, AM 2006. "Antecedents and Consequences of Employee Engagement". *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 21(7). (600-619).
- [25.] Shrivastava, S., Prasad, V. 2019. "Importance of Effective Communication Strategies to Improve Workplace Communication". *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, Vol. 8(3), 161-168.
- [26.] Yusnita, N. 2021. "Does Self-Efficacy Play an Intervening Role? Studying Between Organizational Climate and Job Involvement". *Journal of Humanities and Social Studies*, 05(1), 50-55.